

Tests on S960 steel lap joints with M12 bolts

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the deformation capacity of bolts and plates in lap joints made of high-strength steel, namely S960 steel. The study emphasises the importance of deformation capacity for uniform force distribution between the bolts, which simplifies the design and improves the performance of the joint. The investigation includes a series of tests on bolted lap joints using M12 grade 10.9 bolts, taking into account factors such as bolt shear resistance, manufacturing tolerances and the effects of bolt hole deformation. The results show that Eurocode provisions can lead to unsafe assumptions when connections fail due to bolt shear, with experimental resistances ranging from 83% to 97% of theoretical values. The results emphasise the need for additional design rules for HSS bolted joints and suggest investigating criteria based on minimum shear strength as a function of bolt hole deformation. Ongoing research aims to extend the investigation to lap joints with larger bolt sizes (M16 and M20) and different bolt grades in order to provide comprehensive design guidelines for such critical connections.

Keywords: high strength steel, bolted connections, lap connections, lap joints, bolts, ductility, Eurocode

1 INTRODUCTION

Bolts are normally used in clearance holes, where the clearance allows for fabrication tolerances and simplifies the fabrication and assembly of the joints. In bearing type joints, where the forces are transmitted through the contact between the bolt and the wall of bolt hole, the distribution of forces between all the bolts in the joint is achieved by the ductility of the steel, which allows the bolt to be embedded. The embedding of the bolt is crucial to achieve a uniform distribution of forces between the bolts, which contributes to a uniform utilization of the bolts in shear and thus to simple design rules. Fig. 1 shows a lap joint with 4 bolts, its mechanical model and the distribution of forces between the bolts. The mechanical spring model is usually used to determine the distribution of forces between bolts (1, 2). The spring S_t represents the plate between the bolts in tension, while the equivalent springs S_b represents the bolt in shear and the plate in bearing. The uneven distribution of forces between bolts arises from the compatibility of deformations between two bolts (2, 3). It typically occurs when the elongations of the two springs S_t and S_b are the same order of magnitude. The distribution of forces uniforms when the deformation of spring S_b is much greater than that of spring S_t , which is possible due to different stiffness of the springs. Uneven distribution is characteristic for long joints, for joints with large bolt spacing and for joints with highly stressed plates, which is relevant for high strength steels (HSS) where the elastic elongations can be quite large. The plate in bearing is related to the embedment of the bolt, which leads to elongation of the bolt hole. Since the high strength bolts have only a limited shear deformation capacity, most of the deformation must develop by the elongation of the bolt hole, which can be several orders of magnitude greater than the elongation of the plate in tension. Therefore, a uniform distribution can be assumed as soon as embedding of the bolt is activated. However, the bolts should have sufficient

strength to withstand the bearing forces generated during embedment. Otherwise, the distribution of forces between bolts will remain uneven because the bolt holes cannot deform. Therefore, even in short joints, there may be an uneven distribution of forces between the bolts if the bolts are weak. However, the bolts have some deformation capacity that can in some cases be sufficient for levelling the force on bolts.

Fig. 1 Schemes of lap joint and the possible distribution of forces between bolts

The current and the new Eurocode (4, 5) provide a ductility condition that allows a plastic redistribution of forces between the bolts if the shear resistance of any bolt, taking into account the number of shear planes m , is greater than the bearing resistance at the bolt hole. If the ductility condition is satisfied, the resistance of a group of bolts ΣF_R is taken as the sum of the bearing resistances at the individual bolt holes. It is assumed that the ductility is provided by the deformation of the bolt hole due to the bearing action. If the ductility condition is not met, ΣF_R is taken as the number of bolts n multiplied by the lowest resistance value of any individual bolt, i.e. the shear resistance of the bolt $F_{v,R}$ or the smallest of the bearing resistances at the bolt holes $F_{b,MIN}$.

$$\Sigma F_R = n \cdot \min(mF_{v,R}; F_{b,MIN}) \tag{1}$$

In this case, a uniform distribution of forces between the bolts is assumed. In both cases, i.e. if the ductility condition is fulfilled or not, ΣF_R is reduced by the factor β_{LF} to take into account the non-uniform distribution of forces in long connections. The factor β_{LF} is obtained from:

$$\beta_{LF} = 1 - \frac{L_j - 15d}{200d} \quad \text{but} \quad 0.75 \leq \beta_{LF} \leq 1 \tag{2}$$

where L_j is the distance between the most upstream and the most downstream centres of the bolt holes. The ductility condition as given above may be applied to steel grades greater and equal to S460. For lower grade steels, the ductility condition is less stringent.

The new Eurocode (5) also defines the bearing resistance at bolt hole. Its characteristic value is given as follows:

$$F_b = k_m \alpha_b d t f_u \tag{3}$$

$$\alpha_b = \begin{cases} \min\left(\frac{e_1}{d_0}; 3 \frac{f_{ub}}{f_u}; 3\right) & \text{for end bolt} \\ \min\left(\frac{p_1}{d_0} - \frac{1}{2}; 3 \frac{f_{ub}}{f_u}; 3\right) & \text{for inner bolt} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

$$k_m = \begin{cases} 0.9; & \text{for steel grades} \geq \text{S460} \\ 1; & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

where d is the bolt diameter, d_0 is the diameter of the normal round bolt hole, t is the plate thickness, f_u is the ultimate strength of the plate, f_{ub} is the ultimate strength of bolt, e_1 is the plate end distance and p_1 is the distance between the centres of the bolt holes. The designations correspond to the Eurocode.

The main concern of the bearing type lap joints made of HSS is that the bolts become a weak component. It is therefore difficult to fulfil the ductility condition that can lead to non-ductile failure, such as shearing of the bolts, given by Eq. (1). Although Eq. (1) assumes a uniform force distribution, it is not necessary for it to actually develop. There are two main reasons for this: (i) if the plates in lap joints are highly stressed, the elastic differential strains of the plate lead to an uneven force distribution (see Fig. 1) even in short joints, and (ii) an unfavourable position of the bolt holes due to manufacturing tolerances leads to a non-simultaneous transfer of forces between the bolts, i.e. the contact between the bolts and the holes is not achieved at the same moment. In both cases, levelling can occur if the bolts have good shear ductility (3) or if the deformation of the bolt hole develops due to the bearing action. Since the high-strength bolts (e.g. grade 10.9), commonly used in HSS lap joints have limited deformation capacity and the shear capacity of the bolts is not sufficient to cause the bolt hole deformation, a lower resistance is to be expected than that resulting from Eq. (1). Therefore, additional rules for the design of lap joints would be necessary.

The new Eurocode (5) also provides a force-deformation model for bearing action at the bolt hole (see also (6)). The bearing force, which is the function of the bolt hole elongation u , is for HSS obtained from:

$$F_b(u) = \bar{\sigma}_b(u) d t f_u \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_b(u) = \frac{126u/d}{(1 + \sqrt{30u/d})^2}, \quad \text{but} \quad \bar{\sigma}_b \leq k_m \alpha_b \quad (7)$$

For the above reasons, the experimental investigation was carried out on bolted lap joints made of S960 steel plates. The tests on lap joints with up to 7 M12 bolts are presented in this article.

2 TESTS ON BOLTED LAP JOINTS

2.1 Specimen design

A series of 13 tests on bolted lap joints with M12 bolts is part of a larger ongoing test campaign. The joints (the plates and the bolts) were designed before the material was purchased. Therefore the design was based on mean values for the shear resistance of the bolts taken from the literature (7). The limitation for design of joints was also 1000 kN, which corresponds to the capacity of the testing machine.

Table 1. Average material parameters of 5 mm and 10 mm S960 QL steel plate

Plate thickness	$f_y = R_{p0.2}$ [MPa]	$f_u = R_m$ [MPa]	Elongation A [%]	Contraction Z [%]	E [GPa]
5 mm	973	1047	13.9	52.7	191
10 mm	945	1034	13.8	53.9	175

The joints were designed as lap joints with the bolts in double shear, arranged in the direction of the bearing force. The test specimen is the inner 5 mm or 10 mm thick plate, while the overlap plates are 10 mm thick. The thickness of the overlap plates was sufficient to prevent their deformations. The joint plates were cut from a single 5 mm or 10 mm thick plate so that the bearing force coincided with the direction of plate rolling. The material parameters of the S960 QL plates manufactured in the European Union were determined by a standard tensile test in a certified laboratory. Three tensile samples were taken from each plate in the rolling direction. The material

parameters are shown in *Table 1* and *Fig. 2*. It can be observed that the yield stress was slightly below the nominal value of the yield stress.

Fig. 2. Stress-strain diagrams for 5 mm (left) and 10 mm (right) steel plate

Table 2. Nominal geometry of the specimens

Specimen	t [mm]	b [mm]	Bolt	No. bolts	d_0 [mm]	p_1/d_0	e_1/d_0	p_1 [mm]	e_1 [mm]	Misaligned holes
S01	5	200	M12×60 10.9	7	13	2	1.5	26	19.5	
S01o	5	200	M12×60 10.9	7	14	2	1.5	28	21	1, 4, 7
S05	5	200	M12×60 10.9	6	13	3.5	3	46	39	
S05o	5	200	M12×65 10.9	7	14	3.5	3	49	42	
S05os	5	200	M12×60 10.9	7	14	3.5	3	49	42	1, 4, 7
S05s	5	200	M12×60 10.9	7	13	3.54	3	46	39	1, 4, 7
S12	5	200	M12×65 10.9	7	13	5	3	65	39	
S16o	10	106	M12×60 10.9	7	14	2	1.5	28	21	
S20	10	106	M12×65 10.9	7	13	3.54	3	46	39	
S20o	10	106	M12×65 10.9	7	14	3.5	3	49	42	
S20os	10	106	M12×65 10.9	7	14	3.5	3	49	42	1, 4, 7
S20s	10	106	M12×65 10.9	7	13	3.54	3	46	39	1, 3, 7
S27	10	104	M12×65 10.9	7	13	5	3	65	39	

The joint specimens were designed so that the net cross-section resistance was just below 1000 kN. Therefore, the width of the 5 mm thick specimens was twice as large as the width of the 10 mm thick specimens. The joints were bolted together with M12 10.9 HV bolts (8). The bolts had a sufficient clamping length so that the entire bearing area was on the bolt shank. The number of bolts was chosen so that their shear resistance corresponded approximately to the net cross-section resistance of the specimen. The bolt holes were normal round holes with a diameter of 13 mm and 14 mm in accordance to EN 1090-2 (9). Specimens with 14 mm diameter bolt holes are labelled with an “o” that stands for oversized. According to the Eurocode (5), bolts M12 can be used in 14 mm diameter bolt holes only if the ductility condition is fulfilled. The distance between the bolt holes p_1 was $2d_0$, $3.5d_0$ and $5d_0$. The edge distance e_1 was equal to $1.5d_0$ in combination with $p_1 = 2d_0$ and $e_1 = 3d_0$ for other distances p_1 . The bolt holes were intentionally misaligned for the test specimens labelled with the letter “s”. The numbering of bolts and bolt holes is shown in *Fig. 3*. The outer (B1, B7) and the centre (B4) bolt holes were misaligned in specimens S05s, S20s and S05os, while in specimen S20os the outer (B1, B7) and the third hole (B3) were misaligned. The bolt holes were offset by 1.5 mm and 3 mm for the 13 mm and 14 mm diameter holes respectively. They were offset so that the bolts in the offset holes were the first to transfer the load. The permissible deviation of the bolt hole centre is $\Delta = \pm 2$ mm in accordance with EN 1090-2. The hole

offset of 3 mm can occur for example, if the hole in the inner plate is offset by 1.5 mm and the hole in the outer plate is offset by 1.5 mm in the other direction. The geometry of the test specimens is shown in *Table 2*.

2.2 Test setup

The tests were performed on a universal testing machine with a capacity of 1 MN. The relative displacements between the specimen plate and the overlap plates were measured on both sides of the joint using inductive displacement transducers (LVDTs). The two LVDTs were positioned asymmetrically, as shown in *Fig. 3*. The bolts were tightened by hand so that the plates were in firm contact. A preload of 50 kN was applied before each test, followed by unloading. The tests were then carried out at a prescribed machine displacement rate of 1 mm/min. It was interesting to observe that the bolts fitted into the holes without any problems despite the offset holes. One of the reasons for this was also the extra clearance the bolts provided. The actual bolt diameter was about 11.3 mm, which is the minimum allowable diameter according to (8).

In addition, two series of tests were carried out on single bolt lap joints to determine the shear resistance of the bolts. The bolts tested were M12×60 10.9 and M12×65 10.9. The material properties of the plates and the position of the LVDTs are the same as in the previously described test series of lap joints with multiple bolts. The bolts were preloaded with 20 kN, unloaded and then tested at a prescribed displacement rate of 1 mm/min.

Fig. 3. Test setup

3 ANALYSIS OF TEST RESULTS

The average shear resistances for 2 shear planes of the M12 bolts were determined on the basis of 7 and 8 tests for M12×60 and M12×65. The average shear resistance $F_{V,R}$ and the standard deviation are given in *Table 3*. The standard deviation is around 1.8 % of the average shear resistance, which is about 7 % greater than the characteristic shear resistance according to Eurocode (5). The load-displacement curves of the bolts are shown in *Fig. 4*. All bolts were tested in a double shear configuration with three 10 mm thick plates, with the exception of one M12×60 bolt, which was tested in connection with 5 mm inner plate (curve in *Fig. 4a*). In the test with a 5 mm plate, a large deformation of the bolt hole was observed, while the deformation of the bolt hole in tests with a 10 mm inner plate was about 0.2 mm. *Fig. 5* shows the deformed bolt shortly before fracture. The test was stopped when the force dropped to about 130 kN.

Table 3. Evaluation of shear resistance of M12 bolts for 2 shear planes

Bolts	No. tests	$F_{V,R}$ [kN]	St. dev. [kN]
M12×60 10.9	7	145.8	2.7
M12×65 10.9	8	143.9	2.6

Fig. 4. Load displacement curves of joints for determination of shear resistance of bolts

Fig. 5. Two bolts M12x65 10.9 beyond its maximum resistance

Table 4 shows the maximum resistances of the lap joints F_u , the average force on the bolt at maximum resistance $F_{v,avg}$, their failure mode and the resistances according to the Eurocode, where the governing criterion is the minimum of the Eurocode resistances. The values were calculated using measured the material strengths and nominal geometric dimensions according to Eqs. (1)-(5). The force-displacement curves are shown in Fig. 6, while the photos of selected specimen after failure are shown in Fig. 7. The ductility condition was met for joints S01 and S01o with a short distance between bolts of $2d_0$. Both joints developed large hole elongations and failed due to fracture of the plate in front of the bolt Fig. 7a). The change in slope of the force-deformation curve of S01 shown in a) was caused by an unintentional misalignment of holes due to manufacturing tolerances. The bolt holes in the overlap plates were outside the axis. Therefore, the deformation of the bolt holes allowed a redistribution of the bearing forces between all the bolts.

Significant elongation of the bolt holes was also observed in joints S05, S05s, S05o and S05os (5 mm thick). The S05 joint consisted of 6 bolts, the others of 7 bolts. As expected, S05, S05s and S05os failed due to fracture of the bolts. The resistance was characterised by slightly uneven distribution of forces between the bolts, as the average force on the bolt is lower compared to the shear resistance of the bolt. The load displacement curves of joints with offset bolt holes S05s and S05os shown in Fig. 6b) clearly show (change in the slope of the response curve) that the force was initially transmitted by only three bolts. It appears that part of the plastic deformation at a resistance of about 400 kN is due to the shear deformation of the bolts that initially transferred the load. These bolts have exhausted their deformation capacity to redistribute the forces at maximum resistance, which can be observed by comparing $F_{v,avg}$ in Table 4 for S05, S05s, S05o and S05os. In S05, all bolts failed simultaneously, while in S05s and S05os bolts in the offset holes failed first. In the latter joints, the average force on the bolt in both joints was significantly lower than in S05 (see Table 4). All the bolts fractured in both shear planes (see Fig. 7b)). Joint S05o failed due to the fracture of the net cross-section. As bearing contacts were formed simultaneously, the bolt hole diameter of 14 mm had no influence on the resistance. Fig. 7b), c) show that all bolts were significantly deformed, which means that the shear strength and deformation capacity of the bolts was also exhausted. The plate of specimen S12 was 5 mm thick with large distance between bolts

$p_1 = 5 d_0$. Its behaviour was similar to S05o, with significant elongations of the bolt hole and significant plastic shear deformation of bolts.

Table 4. Test results of lap joints and determination of resistances according to Eurocode

Spec.	F_u [kN]	$F_{v,avg}$ [kN]	Failure mode	β_{lf}	α_b edge	α_b inner	$\beta_{LF} \Sigma F_b$ [kN]	$\beta_{LF} n \times F_{v,R}$ [kN]	$F_{R,net}$ [kN]	Governing criterion	F_R	F_u/F_R
S01	642.8	91.8	Bearing	1.00	1.5	1.5	593.5	1020.5	978.7	Bearing	593.5	1.08
S01o	675.1	96.4	Bearing	1.00	1.5	1.5	593.5	1020.5	973.4	Bearing	593.5	1.14
S05	832.8	138.8	B-ALL	0.98	3	3	997.3	857.4	978.7	Bolts	857.4	0.97
S05o	983.5	140.5	Net	0.95	3	3	1130.6	959.6	973.4	Bolts	959.6	1.02
S05os	834.2	119.2	B7, B1, B4	0.95	3	3	1130.6	972.0	973.4	Bolts	972.0	0.86
S05s	912.8	130.4	B7, B4, B-all	0.96	3	3	1141.0	981.0	978.7	Net	978.7	0.93
S12	994.5	142.1	Net	0.91	3	3	1083.1	919.3	978.7	Bolts	919.3	1.08
S16o	978.8	139.8	Net	1.00	1.5	1.5	1172.6	1020.5	951.3	Net	951.3	1.03
S20	872.8	124.7	B-ALL	0.96	3	3	2254.2	968.4	961.6	Net	961.6	0.91
S20o	986.9	141.0	Net	0.95	3	3	2233.7	959.6	951.3	Net	951.3	1.04
S20os	432.6	61.8	B7, B1 B3	0.95	3	3	2233.7	959.6	951.3	Net	951.3	0.45
S20s	795.2 (710)	113.6 (101)	B7, B1 → unload	0.96	3	3	2254.2	968.4	961.6	Net	961.6	0.83
S27	972.7	139.0	Net	0.91	3	3	2139.9	919.3	940.9	Bolts	919.3	1.06

The 10 mm thick specimens had a similar net cross-section resistance, but a much higher bearing resistance. However, much lower bolt deformation of the holes due to the bearing were expected for the 10 mm thick specimens, as the force-deformation behaviour for bearing is significantly nonlinear. According to the force-deformation model for bearing given by Eqs (6)–(7), the M12 bolt at its maximum shear resistance causes about 3.2 mm elongation of bolt hole in 5 mm thick plate and only 0.5 mm in 10 mm thick plate. In fact, the expected deformation of the bolt hole with 10 mm thick plate is even smaller, as part of the deformation is taken over by the bolt (bolt in shear and the bearing at bolt hole can be represented by two springs connected in series). Specimens S16o, S20o and S27 all failed in the net cross-section (Fig. 6c)). The difference between the joints lay in the distances between the bolt holes p_1 , which were $2 d_0$, $3.5 d_0$ and $5 d_0$. Fig. 7d) shows very clearly that the deformation of the bolt hole due to bearing is barely visible, while the bolts are significantly deformed, comparable to the deformed bolt in Fig. 5, where the deformation state of the bolt is shown just before a complete shear fracture. It can be assumed that the plastic deformation of the bolts levelled the uneven distribution of forces that would lead to the failure of the outer bolts and has redistributed the bearing forces. However, the deformation capacity of the bolts in shear is limited and can only partially contribute to the redistribution of forces. This can be clearly observed in S20 and S20s, both with bolts in 13 mm holes. The bolt holes of the overlap plates of joint S20 were undeliberately misaligned due to manufacturing tolerances, while the holes of S20s were intentionally offset. During the testing of S20, slippage occurred between the specimen and the jaws of the testing machine. Therefore, the test was performed in two stages. In the first stage, the maximum resistance could not be reached. The slip occurred at around 760 kN. The force dropped to around 680 kN (see Fig. 6d)). The joint was unloaded after the third slip occurred. The pressure in the test jaws was increased before the second stage began, when the joint slipped once at around 830 kN. After the first slip, the resistance increased until the joint failed. The dashed line in Fig. 6d) shows the response curve where the slip was subtracted. Similarly, the slip was also preset in the test of S16o (Fig. 6c)). The effect of the unintentionally offset holes of S20 can be seen in the force-displacement curve of the first stage in Fig. 6d), where the load was distributed to all the bolts due to the (plastic) shear deformation of the bolts. The remaining deformation capacity was spent on the redistribution of the forces to level the forces on bolts. This led to the simultaneous shear failure of all bolts at relatively low resistance of 872.8 kN. The

average force on the bolt was only 124.7 kN, which correspond to approximately 87 % of the bolt resistance in shear. The failure was non-ductile and explosive, as the force immediately decreased from about 870 kN to 0 kN. The behaviour of S20s, where the bolt holes were deliberately offset, is very interesting and indicates a case that may not covered by the Eurocode design rules. The misalignment of the bolt holes can be clearly seen in *Fig. 6d*). After bolt B7 fractured at 710 kN, the resistance of the joint continued to increase until it began to decrease at 795.2 kN, indicating that the bolts were about to break. The joint was unloaded, to prevent a sudden failure of all bolts. Bolt B7 fractured only in one shear plane, which is consistent with the decrease in resistance seen in the response curve in *Fig. 7e*). It also shows that bolt B1 practically sheared off. The misalignment of the bolt holes was more pronounced in S20os with bolt hole diameters of 14 mm. As the requirements for a large deformation to distribute the forces over all bolts were not met by either the bolts or the bolt holes, the maximum resistance of the joint was only 432.6 kN. Bolt B7 failed first, then bolts B1 and B3 failed together. The test was stopped after three bolts failed. The 4 remaining bolts were not deformed, and the bolt holes showed only insignificant deformation. If the test had been continued after the failure of 3 bolts, the resistance would not have exceeded $4 \times 140 \text{ kN} = 560 \text{ kN}$, which is about 60 % of the expected resistance (see *Table 4*).

Fig. 6. Load displacement curves of the joints

Table 4 also contains the resistances determined by the Eurocode. The resistance of the lap joints F_R is obtained as the minimum between the net cross-section resistance $F_{R,net}$ and the resistance of the group of bolts. The resistance of the group of bolts is determined as the minimum between the sum of the bearing resistances per bolt hole (obtained from *Eq. (3)*) and the number of bolts n multiplied

by the average shear resistance $F_{v,R}$ of the bolts from *Table 3*. The resistance of the group of bolts is also reduced by the coefficient β_{LF} , which takes into account the uneven distribution of forces between the bolts (see *Eq. (2)*). Since M12 bolts in bolt holes with a diameter of 14 mm should only be used in joints where the bearing resistance is less than the shear resistance of the bolts, the calculation should not be adopted for joints labelled “o” and “os”. The resistances were determined with the nominal values of the geometry parameters and with the average measured tensile strength of the plates f_u (*Table 1*) and the average measured shear resistance of the bolts (*Table 3*). The results show that the bearing resistance of joints S01 and S01o and the net cross-section resistance of S05o, S12, S16o, S20o and S27 is reasonably estimated. On the contrary, the theoretical resistance is always lower than the experimental one if the experimental resistance was determined by the failure of the bolts. In the worst case, the theoretical resistance is overestimated by 20 % (0.83^{-1}). Considering that the overstrength of bolts is only 7 % and that the recommended value of $\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$, the experimental resistance is quite close to the design resistance.

Fig. 7. Specimens after failure

4 CONCLUSION

The paper deals with the requirements for the deformation capacity of bolts and plates in bolted lap joints made of high-strength steel S960. The deformation capacity is not only important for the plastic redistribution of forces, but also for levelling the forces on the bolts when the joint is in the elastic range. The uniform distribution of forces simplifies the design. The resistance of group of bolts ΣF_R in the lap joint complies with Eurocode (5) and is based on the ductility condition. If the ductility condition is not met, the uniform distribution of forces is assumed and ΣF_R is the product of the number of bolts and the shear resistance of the bolts. The tests on S960 lap joints bolted with grade 10.9 M12 bolts showed that the assumption of uniform force distribution was on the unsafe side every time the joint failed due to bolt shear, with the experimental resistance ranging from 83% to 97% of the theoretical resistance. Although the manufacturing tolerances for the position of the bolt holes met the requirements of EN 1090-2, the bolts did not have sufficient deformation capacity to equalise the forces. They were also not strong enough to cause the bearing deformation at the bolt holes, which would also equalise the forces.

Although only 13 tests are shown, they clearly indicate the need for additional design rules for HSS bolted joints. Further research is needed to provide reliable design guidance. However, the solution could be to prescribe the minimum shear resistance of bolts based on the bolt hole deformation criterion.

Experimental investigation of lap joints with M16 and M20 bolts will continue, investigating the behaviour of the joints with different grades of bolt.

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